

QR Code Based Image Steganography

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Abstract-- This paper focuses on QR code-based image steganography, aiming to investigate the potential of QR codes in delivering a large payload capacity while assessing their impact on image quality through various steganographic techniques. The study further explores the utilization of frequency domain steganography technology, specifically employing a discrete wavelet transform-based QR picture steganography method. The primary objective of this research is to protect the Quick Response (QR) code from being visually detected by unauthorized third parties using steganography techniques. By embedding secret information within the QR code, this study aims to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the encoded data. The investigation involves analyzing different steganographic approaches to determine their effectiveness in concealing the embedded information within the QR code. Moreover, the research explores the application of frequency domain steganography, specifically employing the discrete wavelet transform, to enable efficient and secure hiding of data within the QR code. This method provides an opportunity to achieve high capacity and robustness while minimizing the perceptual impact on the QR code and the host image. The findings of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the potential of QR code-based image steganography as a means of secure data transmission. The research outcomes will shed light on the influence of QR codes on payload capacity and image quality, as well as the effectiveness of employing the discrete wavelet transform for QR picture steganography. These insights can be valuable in enhancing the security and privacy of sensitive information transmitted through QR codes while maintaining their usability and visual appeal.

Keywords: QR Code, Steganography, Quick response

I. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

In today's digital era, people communicate information using various communication technologies like the internet, resulting in a significant amount of data being transferred through numerous web services. This data holds great sensitivity and must be protected against interception by adversaries during transmission (Allan, 2018). Steganography involves concealing data within different types of multimedia carriers, such as video clips, digital pictures, audio files, or even text. Once embedded within any of these cover media, the information is referred to as a stego-object. The result of embedding the information in the cover medium is known as a stego-image or stego-video, depending on whether it is an image or video file (Cheddad, 2010). Moreover, steganography is both an art and a science that revolves around hiding messages within seemingly innocent cover materials like text, pictures, or videos. Covert writing is employed in steganography for two main purposes: avoiding detection of the data and preventing its removal through techniques like watermarking and fingerprinting. In these applications, data is hidden within a host dataset and needs to be successfully transmitted to the intended receiver (Forczmanski, 2008).

In today's digital environment, both encryption and steganography are utilized to protect data from unintended recipients or intruders. Consequently, the authors of this text advocate for employing multilayer security that leverages the capabilities of steganography. The concept of steganography can be applied using various widely available formats worldwide, such as JPEG, GIF, PNG, etc., which are suitable for hiding secret messages due to their prevalence on the internet. Weaknesses in cryptography, leading to security breaches, have spurred interest in steganography research (Muhammad et al., 2017). Numerous methods have recently been introduced to hide information within images while preserving their quality. This study focuses on QR-based image steganography techniques because the host image has low communication costs and a high number of redundant bits. In an image, the brightness or pixel values are represented as an array of values at different positions (Kachera, 2017).

Image steganography has diverse applications, especially in today's technologically advanced society. Privacy and confidentiality concerns are prominent among internet users, and image steganography enables secret communication between two individuals (Kamred, 2018). It also facilitates digital copyright protection by utilizing the message as a digital watermark. Another significant application of image steganography is the secure transfer of high-level or top-secret documents between international governments (Phad et al., 2019). In the medical field, practitioners can embed information like the patient's name, remarks, or diagnosis into medical imaging and examinations. E-commerce can employ steganographic techniques to conceal registration information within electronic documents, aiding in authentication (Wang and Ye, 2020). However, spatial algorithms used in image processing, such as cropping, resizing, and rotation, make them susceptible to certain vulnerabilities. Addressing these issues is of utmost importance and requires ongoing progress (Johnson, 2018).

Several studies have focused on QR code image steganography methods. One well-known approach involves replacing the secret message with a Block based Discrete Wavelet transform. This method directly overwrites the steganography technique plane of the cover image with the secret bit stream using a pseudorandom number generator for embedding (exact reference not provided). However, according to Subhedar and Mankar (2018), QR code-based steganography methods have limitations. They are vulnerable to minor changes resulting from image processing operations like cropping, rotation, scaling, and resizing. A steganography algorithm based on QR steganography with Sobel edge detection was found to have poor resilience. When the stego-image underwent manipulations such as cropping, resizing, and rotation, the secret message was destroyed. Therefore, there is a need for an enhanced image steganography method that is resistant to image manipulations and operates in the domains of cryptography and steganography.

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Digital images are commonly used for image steganography, but the size of the cover image is not a significant factor as it reduces the embedding capacity. However, concealing secret data within the cover picture can easily change the features of the image, attracting the attention of unauthorized individuals. The embedding capacity and fidelity (stego picture quality) are crucial components of an image steganographic system, but they often conflict with each other. Achieving an effective steganographic system requires finding a balance between these two aspects.

II. CONCEPT OF STEGANOGRAPHY

Steganography, a field within information hiding, has seen a rise in research works. It has become a popular method for exchanging information, especially with the advancement of Internet technology, and has been around for many years. The term "steganography" originates from the Greek words "steganos," meaning "covered," and "graphein," meaning "to write." While steganography is distinct from cryptography, it serves as another means of ensuring the confidentiality of information during transmission (Michael and Herbert, 2011). It achieves this by concealing the existence of secret communication from potential attackers. The secret messages are hidden within digital objects that appear inconspicuous to human perception, and only those with the stego-key can extract the message from the stego-object at the intended destination (Rodrigues et al., 2004).

The objective of steganography is to hide the presence of secret communication (Zenati, W. Ouarda, A. Alimi, 2020) by inserting the secret data into a cover image without causing noticeable changes to it (Malik et al., 2017). This process results in a stego image, where the secret data is embedded within the cover image (Shah and Bichkar, 2018). In image steganography, the primary goal is to minimize the differences between the stego and cover images (Biswas et al., 2019). Key parameters used to evaluate steganography techniques include imperceptibility, payload capacity, and security (Subhedar et al., 2014). However, optimizing all these parameters simultaneously is challenging. Increasing payload capacity, for instance, often compromises imperceptibility and security (Hussain et al., 2018). Similarly, enhancing any of the parameters can have a detrimental effect on the remaining two.

The most commonly used digital steganography technique is LSB (Least Significant Bit) replacement steganography (Mukherjee and Sanyal, 2019). Many spatial domain image steganography techniques are based on LSB steganography, with modifications. In LSB steganography, the secret data bits replace the LSBs of the cover image pixels. The number of LSBs replaced is determined by the amount of secret data to be embedded. The secret data can be inserted in all the pixels or selectively in specific pixels, with the information for these selected pixels provided through a secret stego-key (Cheddad et al., 2010). Various variants of this traditional technique have emerged, where authors have used image features like edges, textures, brightness, intensity levels, etc., to determine the amount of data to be hidden (Yang and Sun, 2009).

Some researchers have even proposed inserting additional redundant random bits alongside the secret data bits to align the histogram of the stego image with that of the cover image. One example is the LSB+ technique, although it reduces the data embedding capacity. Qazanfari et al. (2016) introduced an enhanced version of the LSB+ technique, which identifies sensitive pixels and avoids inserting LSB data in higher-order bits, thereby improving imperceptibility and data concealment (Qazanfari, 2016).

Figure 1: Image Steganography processes.

A. QR code fundamentals

A QR Code is a type of barcode that can be scanned both vertically and horizontally. It allows for the storage of more data compared to traditional one-dimensional barcodes. However, using a QR Code requires a more advanced reader.

The ISO/IEC 18004 industrial standard defines QR Code, but it was originally created and protected by the Japanese company Denso Wave in 1994. The main goal of QR Code development was to make it easy for users to encode and read information. Denso Wave released QR Code to the world in 1994 and still holds the patent rights for it. The developers intended for QR Code to be used by as many people as possible, without any cost or concerns about potential problems. Thanks to advancements in mobile technology, QR Code has gained widespread popularity in commercial settings. The global penetration rate of mobile devices increased from 15.6% in 2001 to 74.9% in 2010. Almost all mobile phones in Japan are capable of reading QR Codes, and countries like South Korea and Europe are catching up, while the United States is relatively slower in adoption.

The iPhone, Google's Android operating system, Windows Mobile phones, and Nokia's phones all offer internet access and camera capabilities, enabling them to scan and decode QR Codes (Watson, 2014). QR Codes play a pivotal role in bridging the virtual and real worlds, transforming marketing methods. They provide an opportunity to engage with consumers and promote brands. Previous research highlights the need for effective marketing campaigns to raise consumer awareness through QR Codes. Two implementation frameworks are presented to illustrate this: one based on product or service involvement, and the other on marketing communication systems (Boehm, 2014).

Currently, QR Codes have become a common means of communication with potential customers through print media in many countries. They are found on stickers, booths, business cards, and advertisements. When attendees at a tradeshow come across a booth with a QR Code, their attention is captured. By scanning the QR Code with their smartphones, they are automatically directed to the company's webpage, where they can access detailed information (Cheddad, 2010). The use of QR Codes is driven by their novelty and uniqueness. They offer immediate access to information and entertainment in the virtual environment. The convenience and speed of QR Codes further contribute to their popularity. Additionally, QR Codes can deliver information instantly to mobile phones, regardless of the user's location (Elham, 2013).

B. QR Code Characteristics:

The characteristics of QR Codes are outlined below, providing insights into their basic principles.

a) High data encoding capacity:

Traditional barcodes are one-dimensional, meaning scanners scan them horizontally, regardless of the barcode's height. This limited one-dimensional format restricts the amount of information that can be stored, typically fewer than 20 characters (Cole, 2013).

In contrast, QR Codes have a significantly higher capacity for storing information. They can store multiple times the amount of data compared to traditional barcodes. QR Codes are capable of storing various types of data, including numeric and alphabetic characters, languages such as Korean, Japanese, and Chinese (kanji, kana, hiragana), symbols, binary code, and control codes. Moreover, a single QR Code can store up to 7,089 characters (Fridrich, 2009). Figure (2.2) provides an illustration of a QR Code encoding numeric and alphabetic characters.

Figure 2: An example of the QR Code encodes numeric and alphabetic characters

Figure (2) displays that the different alphabetic characters and numerics are encoded in a QR Code. Although the size of the symbol is small, it can store amount of information.

b) Compact printout size:

Unlike one-dimensional barcodes, QR Codes can store information in both the horizontal and vertical directions. This enables QR Codes to occupy only 25% of the space required by one-dimensional barcodes when storing the same amount of data (Hong, 2012).

c) Kanji and kana compatibility:

QR Codes transform information into an image format to optimize space utilization. Since QR Codes were developed in Japan, they are particularly well-suited for handling kanji and kana characters. QR Code

encoding aligns with the Japanese industrial standards level 1 and level 2 for kanji character sets. It efficiently encodes one kana or kanji character in just 13 bits. Compared to other two-dimensional codes, QR Codes can store more than 20% additional data. Figure (2.4) illustrates how various kanji and kana characters can be converted into QR Code symbols, allowing for efficient data storage (Reference for figure not provided).

Figure 3: Kanji and Kana is converted to QR Code.

d) *QR code storage capacity and error correction:*

The storage capacity of a QR Code is influenced by various factors, including the QR Code version, its size, the level of error correction, and the type of encoded data. The key components of a QR Code are the data segment and the error correction code-words. The data segment consists of multiple segments encoded using different methods, each with its own unique mode. Identifying the data code-words segment and the error correction code-words segment is relatively straightforward once the QR Code version and error correction level are known. It's important to note that the length of the information part doesn't necessarily correspond to the actual length of the data. Padding patterns are used to fill up the information length (Johnson, 2018). QR Codes possess error correction capabilities, allowing them to handle image contamination and damage. Even when a QR Code image is partially dirty or damaged, the error detection mechanisms can focus on correcting the affected areas. In general situations, data can be recovered even if a portion of the code is compromised. However, there may be instances where data restoration is not possible if the image is heavily contaminated or damaged. Figure (2.4) illustrates the impact of dirt and damage on QR Codes. In this study, the use of digital QR codes helps address this issue (Kamred, 2014).

Figure .4: Dirt and damage of QR Code.

The QR Code can be effectively corrected even if certain segments of the code become unreadable due to dirt or damage. This allows for easy data restoration in such situations. When dealing with incomplete QR Codes, there are four levels of error detection that can be selected for error correction. Factors to consider when choosing an error correction level include the QR Code's size, operating conditions, available space, and the level of environmental control (Imaculate, 2014). These four levels, known as Reed-Solomon error correction levels, are denoted as L, M, Q, and H in increasing order of capacity. Here are their corresponding error correction capabilities:

- Level L can correct approximately 7% or fewer errors.
- Level M can correct approximately 15% or fewer errors.
- Level Q can correct approximately 25% or fewer errors.
- Level H can correct approximately 30% or fewer errors.

In terms of error correction capacity, Level L has the lowest, while Level H has the highest capacity.

QR Code possesses the ability to be read from any direction in a 360-degree range. Unlike traditional one-dimensional barcodes that have a limited reading angle of around ten degrees, QR Code can be read from any direction and at high speed. The positioning of detection patterns at the corners of the symbol allows QR Code to be quickly located and read, even in the presence of background interference (Ibaida, 2010).

QR Code also offers a structured appending feature, allowing various data areas to be classified. Multiple QR Code symbols can be combined to store a large amount of information. A single data symbol can be divided into a maximum of 16 symbols, providing convenience for printing. Figure (2.6) illustrates the structured appending feature of QR Code, demonstrating how multiple QR Codes can be stored within a single QR Code (Mali, 2012).

Figure 5: Structured appending of QR Code.

III. A REVIEW OF RELEVANT WORKS IN THIS TOPIC

Alam and Islam (2013) proposed the use of SDS (Sieve Division Shuffle) and Medical Imaging techniques to compare the accuracy of transmitted data and authenticate the sender SDS. However, it was observed that the performance of Peak Signal to Noise Ratio was not satisfactory for standard datasets. Geetha et al. (2014) implemented an Edge Detection Method using Gaussian filter, Dimensional convolution filter, Multiple Error Replacement, and Variable Embedding Ratio. Their work achieved good visual qualities, high embedding capacity, and enhanced security.

Jose and Abraham (2015) applied Image Encryption, Chaotic sequence, and pseudorandom number steganographic techniques to achieve higher data hiding capacity. Kadam et al. (2016) employed AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) with a 128-bit key and 32-bit words to prevent unauthorized access to secret files. They also highlighted increased data security, protecting decryption keys from hackers. However, their work had the limitation of requiring minimal memory for implementation.

Mahato et al. (2017) utilized HTML attributes and Stegno-crypto techniques, exploiting the rich code of HTML for steganography and easy communication through the internet. However, their work faced limitations in terms of increased algorithm complexity and the inability to extract the secret message. Ramaiya et al. (2018) employed various steganographic methods and demonstrated that varying the two least significant bits (LSB) of each pixel does not affect the quality of the cover image.

Samidlw and Agrawal (2019) used techniques such as LSB, Raster Scan, Random Scan, Layout Management, and Spatial Domain to show that pixels can be used to hide data. They also extended this technique to any location within the image and any dimension or shape. Thenmozhi and Chandrascka (2020) utilized 2-D DWT, $M \times N$ size cover image, and the Henon Map to ensure high capacity and good invisibility of hidden data. However, their work faced the limitation of being unable to extract the secret message while completely removing the outlines of the encrypted images. Luo et al. (2019) employed the pixel value differencing approach and LSBMR (Least Significant Bit Matching Revisited) as a data hiding algorithm. Their technique involved preprocessing the image by dividing it into non-overlapping blocks and rotating them. The selected units for data hiding were determined based on a threshold parameter. Postprocessing was then performed to obtain the stego-image.

In conclusion, various research studies have been conducted in steganography, and this paper presents a framework for embedding a QR code within an image. The receiver is prompted to enter a username and password generated by the sender to unlock the hidden message.

IV. Methodology

In this section of the research, the methods used to achieve the objectives of this work were outlined. The section further explains the approach taken and the reasons for choosing the research method. Specifically, an algorithm for enhancing image steganography using LSBMR (Least Significant Bit Modification and Replacement) with Sobel edge detection was presented in this section.

This study proposes a method called QR code-Input field which aims to protect digital documents' authenticity and integrity against alteration and tampering by generating an input field that requires receivers to input "USERNAME" and "PASSWORD" to reveal hidden message in a QR code. The QR code-Input field is a novel method which protects the QR code component of digital documents. This will be discussed in details in chapter Four. The outcome of this method is an input field which is inside a Quick response Code (QR code) to form a digital User-Password authentication. Below is the flow of the propose framework.

V. QR CODE APPLICATION APPROACH

In this method one QR code image are used. The image represents the converted text of the secret message to QR code then changing the inverse of dot's color in two special important areas (between the detection patterns); i.e, the white dot is substituted with black dot and vice versa. To guarantee an exact retrieving to the original message from the encrypted QR, one of the reversible logic operators is used. The selected one is the inverter operator which provides this feature and suites to obtain from cipher text the original plain text.

VI. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The use of QRCode system for secure data transfer through steganography is an efficient approach to concealing data through a hidden channel. This system is designed to function independently without the need for a database or web server. Its main operations include message hiding and message extraction. The implementation of the system was carried out on a Windows 10 Operating System, utilizing a 2.27 GHz Intel Core i7 processor with 8 GB of 350 MHz DDR3 memory. The application allows users to provide the message you want to hide in a QRcode, embed the QR code in the image, enter the email of the recipient, create username and password then send. Finally, the receiver can extract secret message from the stego-image using one of the two steganographic methods as can be seen in Figure 7

Figure 7: Home page of the system

i. *Message Hiding*

The following description was used to embed a secret message in a cover QRCode. The user has to first type the secret message in the text area in the top of the application. Select an encode to generate the QRCode. Then click on the techniques to be used for conducting steganography. The stego-image is produced and displayed under the QRCode Stego-Image. Finally, the stego-image is embedded by the user as stego-im.gif. Figure 8 depicts the snapshot for message hiding with the techniques.

Figure 8: Message box and the encoded image

Immediately the send message has been pressed as shown in figure 9, a mail will be forwarded to the recipient email address starting that an QRCode containing the embedded message has been sent with a link to follow to decode the message.

Figure 9: Recipient login details page

ii. Message Extraction

The following description shows the technique employed to extract a secret message from a QRCode image. First the receiver must have received an open mail to view the link, clicked on the link, entered the required username and password, and finally had the message displayed. The extracted secret message is displayed at the top right corner of the application while the image appears at the right bottom end. Figure 9 depicts the snapshot for message extraction using the techniques.

Figure 9: Message contents box containing the encoded message

After the link has been clicked, a new separate window will open where the recipient will have to input the assigned username and password to have access to the embedded message inside the QRCode.

Figure 10: Recipient login details of the system

The performance of the system was tested with different images and compared with the work of Zohreh and Jihad, (2014) in line with the stated objectives of our research. The comparative performance and security of the designed system was based on the following features: robustness, undetectability, embedding (payload) capacity and invisibility.

iii. Result discussion

In practical applications, various versions of QR codes are used, each with its own data capacity. The size of the text data being converted into a QR code affects the size of the black squares (modules) in the QR code image. When the data size is large, the black square area in the QR code image for the secret message becomes smaller. Conversely, when the data size is small, the black square area in the QR code image for the secret message becomes larger. This can be observed in the examples shown in Figure 4.1, 4.3, and 4.5 in the table description, where the size of the black square in the secret message QR code has a significant impact. Consequently, this results in the generation of a new QR code with either low or high image steganography, depending on whether the black square size in the secret message QR code is small or large.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, several important findings and conclusions were drawn from this research:

1. The proposed method effectively hides message contents with minimal processing time by reducing the compression process, resulting in lower time complexity.
2. The QR image code method yields more satisfactory results compared to the first method, as it can be applied to all versions of QR codes.
3. Image steganography techniques are preferable as they produce readable QR codes.
4. There is minimal difference between the original QR code of the cover and the stegoQR code after the embedding process.
5. Previous techniques were ineffective when dealing with high versions of QR codes due to the increased amount of details in the message QR code. However, the second and third methods can be applied to all versions of QR codes for the purpose of encryption or concealment.

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197

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